

USE OF INTERACTIVE EXERCISES OF THE LEARNINGAPPS SERVICE IN TEACHING THE DISCIPLINE "FINANCE"

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the possibilities of using the LearningApps service, presents its positive aspects for both students and teachers, provides practical examples of creating different interactive exercises for use in teaching the discipline "Finance".

In modern conditions of transformations in the system of higher education, individual elements of distance learning are increasingly used in the course of teaching certain disciplines. Modern information and communication technologies are becoming an integral part of the implementation of almost any activity of teachers and students. To organize their activities, professors and teachers of higher educational institutions should [1-7]:

- have a certain level of knowledge in the field of information and communication technologies and be able to apply them in practice, while improving their skills by adapting the educational material to the new realities of the organization of the educational process;
- be able to use the main programs included in the basic set of Microsoft Office programs;
- actively work on the Internet, study the content of various information and educational sites, have the skills to search and work with large amounts of data;
- be able to develop electronic training courses for use in various educational environments, structure the educational material, compose questions, tests, assignments, control the work of students.

The purpose of this work is to show the possibilities of using the LearningApps service simulators as an electronic resource with interactive tasks in teaching the discipline "Finance".

The study of the capabilities of the LearningApps service simulators was carried out by analyzing the scientific literature and practice use of the functionality of the service, observing and summarizing pedagogical experience, testing various tools during lectures and practical lessons. As a basis for the study, theoretical and practical developments were considered,

which make it possible to study the tools of the LearningApps service. Let's consider the positive aspects of using the service for students and teachers [8-12].

LearningApps simulators have great features for students, including:

- interactivity and the possibility of application in the work in the classroom and outside the classroom;
- individual trajectory of the task, focused on the level of student training;
- the possibility of repeated repetition of each exercise;
- the possibility of multiple use;
- a variety of types of exercises to perform exercises.

The benefits of the server for teachers include:

- free access to the service;
- multilingual interface, including the ability to work in English, Russian, German and other languages;
- a large number of different templates that allow the use of simulators at all stages of the lesson when studying different topics;
- easiness of use of exercise templates that you can do yourself or follow the example of existing ones;
- ability to do both separate exercises and combine several exercises into one collection of exercises both on one topic and on one discipline module
- opportunity to get acquainted with the exercises of other teachers, which are posted in the public domain;
- ability to embed exercises in any program, website or blog. Prepared exercises can be presented to students on a computer, laptop, tablet or smartphone screens, paper, using links and QR codes.

LearningApps is a service for electronic support of the learning process using interactive simulators. The goal of the project is to create a collection of interactive applications that are not tied to any educational platform. Let's discuss several examples of interactive exercises. Figure 1 shows the "Let's guess" puzzle. The exercise uses 28 different financial concepts and processes. Students should divide them into 4 categories "Financial relations", "Name of money funds", "Items of current consumption", and "Financial investments". Students must activate one of the categories by clicking on it, and then click on each term they think belongs to that category. If students make the correct choice, the puzzle box will disappear, if they make a mistake, they will receive an error notification and will have to choose another category for this term.

Figure 1. Example of the interactive exercise – puzzle “Let’s guess”

Figure 2 shows the example of the “Find a Pair” exercise. This template allows you to create an exercise on the correlation of any two elements. This exercise uses terms from the category “Economic entities” and the corresponding terms for each of them from the category “Money funds”. Students should select one economic entity and determine which money fund corresponds to that entity. Students must combine both terms. If they make the right choice, then both items will immediately disappear, if not, then they will have to make another attempt.

Figure 2. Example of the interactive exercise “Find a Pair”

Figure 3 shows an example of the interactive exercise “Classification”. Students must classify all the terms in the picture between the two categories “Family incomes” and “Family expenses”. Each term should be rearranged to the appropriate category. If the students have rearranged the term correctly, then at the end of the task it will be circled in green. If they made a mistake, then the term will be circled in red. Students will be able to correct their mistakes.

Figure 3. Example of the interactive exercise “Classification”

Figure 4 shows an example of the interactive exercise “Sequence”. This category includes exercises to determine the correct arrangement of components, for example, “Chronological sequence” to determine the chronological order of the location of information fragments, “Arrange in order” to determine the order of words, sentences, texts, pictures, audio. Students must put the actions in the correct order. If the students have correctly arranged the actions, then at the end of the task they will be circled with a green line. If they made a mistake, then this action will be circled in red. At the end of the assignment, students will be able to correct their mistakes.

Figure 4. Example of the interactive exercise “Sequence”

Based on the results of considering the possibilities of the service, reading various articles, developing your own exercises and using them in teaching the discipline "Finance", we can conclude that the LearningApps service is a constantly evolving resource with constantly appearing new templates, a growing collection of applications laid out in the public domain, which reduces the time to create labor-intensive simulators based on ready-made ones.

On the LearningApps website, you need to register, read the recommendations of the developers, get free access to the simulators on the topic of interest, and you can try to create your own exercises. After the exercise has been created, it must be installed and previewed, then finalized or immediately saved to the "My Stuff" folder. The exercise can be used immediately, edited at any time, published, and made available to all users of the service.

This is a simple and affordable option for creating interactive tasks according to instructions or based on ready-made examples. Students can watch, read, solve, and submit exercises from their phone or tablet and do not need a computer. Using this service, teachers can create a variety of interactive exercises, make their lectures and practical classes more interesting and productive.

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